

Futuristic Trends of Management with Emotional Intelligence

Seema Thevar

Teacher, (Anugraha School, Dindigul)

Dr. Mariaponreka

Assistant Professor, (Meenakshi College, Madurai)

Dr. S. Ramesh

*Associate Professor School of Commerce and Management Studies
(Jain Deemed-to-be-University), Bangalore*

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Introduction

Emotions are involved in everything people do: - every action, decision and judgment. Emotionally intelligent people diagnose this and use their thinking to control their emotions rather than being managed by them. In the course of previous two decades, Emotional Intelligence (EI) concept has become a crucially important indicator of a person's knowledge, skills and abilities in the workplace, school and personal life. The overall result of researches suggests that EI plays a significant role in job performance, motivation, decision making, successful management and leadership. Thus applying EI methodology in higher education can have lots of benefits for students.

Emotional Intelligence

Daniel Goleman(1998) defined “Emotional intelligence is the capacity for distinguishing our feelings and those of others, for motivating ourselves, and for managing emotions well in us and our relationships. Emotional intelligence defines abilities distinct from, but complementary to, academic intelligence or the virtuously cognitive capacities measured by IQ”.

Dalip Singh (2003) defines “emotional intelligence as the capability of an individual to appropriately and successfully respond to a huge variety of emotional stimuli is elicited from the inner self and immediate environment. Emotional intelligence constitutes three psychological dimensions: emotional sensitivity, emotional maturity and emotional competency, all of which motivate an individual to recognize truthfully, interpret honestly and handle tactfully the dynamics of human behaviour”.

“Daniel Goleman goes on to propose a framework of particular competence to achieve outstanding performance several of these skills are required, spread out among the five domains: self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy and social skills.”

He defines emotional competence as: - “A learned capability based on emotional intelligence those results in outstanding performance at work”.

Emotional intelligence is the potential for learning these competencies. Being high in emotional intelligence does not guarantee that the person will have the acquired skills necessary to excel in work, it only means that(s) he has a high potential for learning them.

Below is the table that constitutes the heart of the book, and the concepts presented in the table are developed extensively throughout the book by using tens of examples and anecdotes.

The five main competencies are categorized into two main categories: Personal and social skills. Each of the competencies is detailed further and explained into its components and thoroughly explained in the book.

The Emotional Competence Framework																																																											
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Significance of the Study

1. The study focusses on identifying the phenomena related to emotional intelligence among teachers at private educational institutions in Dindigul.
2. The study was carried out to study the association between the demographic profiles of teachers with Emotional Intelligence.
3. It may help to establish social relationships and managing emotions in others. The teachers who have high emotional intelligence communicates with the constructive goal in mind and controls his or her feelings carefully more than reacting to the situation by impulse produced by feelings generated event.

Statement of the Problem

In today's modernized world, the students are more knowledgeable, and the availability of information in social media made them on par with anyone across us. Also, people in all the sectors have become highly knowledge-oriented and especially for teachers it has become mandatory to get them updated till the current time. It also requires a high-level of emotional intelligence to handle students as well as to deal with others to manage our day-to-day life. In this context, emotional intelligence plays an important role of teachers, and it was presumed that emotional intelligence might have been associated with a demographic profile and therefore the present study was undertaken with the question - Does there exist an association between a demographic profile and Emotional intelligence?

Objectives

1. To ascertain the level of emotional intelligence of teachers in Dindigul district
2. To study the association between demographic profile and emotional intelligence

Hypothesis

There is no significant association between demographic profile and emotional Intelligence

Methodology

The study is conducted on Teachers working in Dindigul Colleges both Arts and Engineering. A sample size of 200, to study the Emotional Intelligence was carried using the survey method. The empirical research design is used in this study, and primary data was collected from the faculty members. Empirical research relies on experience or observation alone, often without due regard for system and theory. A mechanism was developed by the researcher to measure the emotional intelligence of faculty working in colleges in Dindigul district. The questionnaire method has been preferred by the researcher for collecting data from the faculty members working in colleges in Dindigul district. The structured questionnaire is framed and systematized in sequence to elicit the response from the target respondents. The questionnaire was designed in such a way to measure the emotional intelligence of teachers. The collected data was entered in the software SPSS, and analyzed through the statistical tool chi-square test and correspondence analysis to achieve the objectives of the study.

Data Analysis

The EI score of the respondents is ranging from 38 to 83 with a mean score of 62.15 and a standard deviation of 7.676 for all the respondents and therefore there is a considerable variation in the EI score among the respondents. The classification of respondents made on statistical basis with respondents above Mean + Standard Deviation of EI score were classified as having "High"

level of EI, the respondents below Mean – Standard Deviation of EI score were classified as having “Low” level of EI and the respondents having their EI score between these two values were classified as having “Medium” level of EI. Among the respondents taken for study, 15 per cent of respondents were classified as having “Low” level of EI, 19 per cent of respondents were classified as having “High” level of EI, and the remaining 66 per cent of respondents were classified as having “Medium” level of EI.

Association between demographic profile and Emotional Intelligence

The result of the Chi-square test is displayed in the table. It can be observed that the association between Emotional intelligence and the demographic variables Gender, Language, Working hours, and Working nature of spouse are not statistically significant ($p > .05$) at 5 per cent level of significance. However, the low p-value ($< .001$) for the demographic variables Age, Marital status, Education, Experience, Type institute, Sector, Area, and Number of dependents and verify that there is a significant association between Emotional intelligence and these variables.

Table 1. Chi-Square Test - Demographic profile VS Emotional Intelligence

Demographic Profile	Chi-square	df	Sig.
Age (in years)	62.288	6	.000*
Gender	1.411	2	.494
Marital status	43.274	4	.000*
Language	5.865	4	.209
Education	37.948	6	.000*
Total experience	82.896	10	.000*
Working hours per week	.572	2	.751
Current experience	40.966	4	.000*
Type of institute	29.544	4	.000*
Sector	29.123	4	.000*
Area	22.293	4	.000*
No. of Dependents	43.679	6	.000*
Spouse working	1.952	2	.377
Spouse working sector	14.882	4	.005*

* Chi-square is significant at 5% level of significance

The association between Emotional intelligence and the demographic variables Gender, Language, Working hours, and Working nature of spouse are not statistically significant. The significant associations found through the chi-square test was further analyzed through correspondence analysis and the following figure is self-explanatory for the associations.

Emotional intelligence VS Age

The proportion of respondents in the High category of EI is more as age of the respondent increases. This suggests that a person's matures with age and older people have more control on their emotional intelligence.

The proportion of respondents in the High category of EI is more in case of married respondents than the other categories of marital status. Also the proportion of divorced/widow respondents in the high level of EI is comparatively less than the respondent in other categories.

Emotional intelligence VS Education

Emotional intelligence VS Experience

The proportion of respondents in the High category of EI is more in case of respondents with Master's degree and Doctoral degree qualification is more than the other categories of education. Therefore it is concluded that the level of emotional intelligence increases with education.

The proportion of respondents with above 10 years of experience are closer to High category of EI and the respondents with 0 to 2 years experience are closer to low level of experience. Therefore it is concluded that the level of emotional intelligence increases with experience.

Emotional intelligence VS Sector

Emotional intelligence VS Type of Institute

The proportion of respondents working in engineering institutions is closer to High category of EI. Therefore it is concluded that the level of emotional intelligence of teachers working in engineering colleges is more than the teachers working in other institutions.

The proportion of respondents working in private institutions is closer to High and Medium category of EI. Also the teachers working in Government and Aided institutions are not closer to

high emotional intelligence. Therefore it is concluded that the level of emotional intelligence of teachers working in engineering colleges is more than the teachers working in other institutions.

EI vs. Area EI VS No. of dependents EI VS Spouse working sector

The proportion of respondents residing in rural area is closer to High level of EI. Therefore it is concluded that the level of emotional intelligence of teachers residing in rural area is more than the teachers residing in other areas.

The proportion of respondents with three numbers of dependents in their families is closer to High level of EI. Also the proportion of respondents with only one number of dependent in their families is closer to Low level of EI. Therefore it is concluded that the number of dependents in the family may also be a factor affecting the level of emotional intelligence of respondents.

The proportion of respondents whose spouse are working in private and other sectors are closer to High level of EI. Also the proportions of respondents with high level EI (whose spouse are working in government sectors) are comparatively lesser. Therefore it is concluded that the teachers whose spouse working in private and other sectors are well supported by them and have higher level of EI.

Implications of the study

The ideas for improving the situation of the teachers

Teachers’ emotional intelligence has an inspiration on the behaviour of the students through their captivating into account of the requirements of their students. It might be important to segment in collective activities at the school, in order to augment teachers’ emotional intelligence by concentrating on consuming greater interaction with the students and learning added about them and how they can help them to complete their aims. The team at the school might help the teachers regarding their hitches with the curriculum by using and developing numerous methods and strategies to teach the students in added convenient way.

The supervisors have an effect on the teachers’ abilities to manage with demands and leave them fewer likely to break down from compact personal accomplishment. They need to be assured that they are interested in working together as they will profit from this. The supervisors should take additional care concerning the teachers, rather than monitoring or appraising them. Some of the supervisors might not understand their role.

They are not responsible for in what way the teachers could or should face the stressful situation. They can support the teachers by giving them more information, by clarifying the roles in the

teaching system and by comforting them that they can deal with their problems by themselves. Within the Syrian culture it is not acceptable for a teacher to tell a supervisor that he does not similar working with him or that he would desire to work with somebody else.

The director of the school also picks the team, which occasionally does not work as it should. It might be valuable for the teachers to express their emotions and explain that they would like to change the team and that perhaps they would be more gratified in another team and not only that they do not like the supervisor as a person. The supervisors should stab to work with the teachers in order to have a positive effect on their personalities and particularly on their emotional intelligence by developing the competences of the teachers in gaining new skills to manage their emotions.

The teachers work in problematic circumstances and this requires a diversity of different emotions in order to manage with such stressful conditions. It would be valuable to know why the teachers have a ration of stress and why they cannot work effectively. It might be that the teachers are not able to discovery a balance between their work and their personal problems or that they are not satisfied with their jobs and are experiencing fatigue.

The schools should recall that the teachers are unwilling to teach extra students than they should or work overly extensively. This pointer to the teachers enduring negative emotions and fetching less satisfied with their jobs. Thus, they would hurt from burnout. Therefore, the schools should request more teachers if they have a deficiency of staff.

Implication-Emotional Intelligence Training must be made a Part of Teacher Training

Because the teachers chief, and teach the upcoming youth, who provide for a wide variety of gradually sophisticated and ever changing diversity of manpower needed, their job is a more accountable one, implying that the teachers be great on EI and well-being to be performing efficiently. Studies stated prior imply that EI can be improved, cultivated through training. Hence the training elements for teachers at all levels must contain components on attractive their Emotional intelligence. An Emotionally Intelligent teacher will be able to:-

Monitor and cope negative emotions like anger, frustration, irritability etc. ... better which will help her remain quiet in the classroom situations which evoke the negative emotions.

Being optimistic-There are individual differences among students and only ancheerful teacher will be able to sustain in her efforts towards the betterment of students who are relatively weak.

Understand emotions among their students helping them to identify students in distress and give them the required attention and refer them for further help if needed.

Conclusion

The study focused on Emotional Intelligence among teachers in Private Educational Institutions in Dindigul District. Study was extended to report the emotional intelligence among teachers based on demographic profile.

It was found that even if Empathy factor score was found low, overall EI scores was relatively higher among the private teachers in Dindigul. Study found that the teachers of private educational institutions have high level of Emotional Intelligence. The high level of EI among teachers indicated that they could identify, assess and control the emotions of self, peers and students in their teaching institution in Dindigul District

These can be better with effective intelligence of the teachers. Thus, it is necessary to create numerous projects, to give teachers more information about burnout and how they can overcome it and understand how they can deal with the problems.

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